

Dyes derived from Quinoline-2-aldehyde.

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Triphenylmethane dyestuffs belonging to the malachite green series have been obtained by condensing alkyl or aryl substituted anilines with various aldehydes including a few heterocyclic aldehydes like furfural. Most of them are of little theoretical importance apart from the fact that being similar in constitution to malachite green, they have analogous properties.

In connection with the effect of a heterocyclic nitrogen atom on colour which has been the subject of a number of communications from this laboratory (*cf.* Tewari and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 161; 1927, 4, 201; 1928, 5, 108), it was thought advisable to try it in the triphenylmethane dyestuffs as has already been tried in the pyronine series. For this purpose the most useful compound to start with would be α -pyridine aldehyde, which on condensation with substituted anilines would give a series of colouring matters strictly comparable to the corresponding dyestuffs obtained from benzaldehyde. Unfortunately α -pyridine aldehyde is such an exceedingly difficult compound to get at that for all intents and purposes its employment in the preparation of dyestuffs is an impracticable affair. Consequently attention was directed to quinoline aldehyde which has been recently prepared and described by Hammick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2882; 1926, 129, 1302). The malachite green series of dyestuffs thus derived from quinoline aldehyde would be strictly comparable to the corresponding dyestuffs obtained from naphthalene aldehyde.

Apart from that consideration it would also be interesting to see whether such dyes which contain a quinoline nucleus have got photosensitising properties just in the same way as cyanine or pinacyanol which has also got a quinoline nucleus in the molecule.

Quinoline-2-aldehyde condenses very easily with mono- or di-substituted anilines in presence of concentrated hydrochloric

acid or zinc chloride with formation of colourless leuco compounds, which can be oxidised to the colouring matter by means of manganese dioxide or lead peroxide. The colouring matters can also be prepared direct without the intermediate formation of leuco compounds by heating quinaldine-tribromide (Hammick, *loc. cit.*) with substituted anilines in presence of zinc chloride or zinc oxide or without any condensing agent at all. The dyestuffs thus obtained are all green or bluish green in colour, very stable toward light and are practically devoid of all photosensitising properties.

The following substituted anilines have been condensed with quinoline aldehyde and the corresponding dyestuff obtained: dimethylaniline, diethylaniline, methylbenzylaniline and ethylbenzylaniline.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tribromoquinaldine.—This was prepared according to the method given by Hammick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2882).

Quinoline-2-aldehyde was prepared from the above by the method recommended by Hammick (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of Quinoline-2-aldehyde and Dimethylaniline.—Quinoline-2-aldehyde (5 g.), dimethyl-aniline (10 g.) and zinc chloride (2 g.) were mixed together and heated for about three hours on water-bath. The excess of dimethylaniline was then removed by steam distillation. The solid residue was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and precipitated by a dilute solution of sodium carbonate. The dark brown leuco base obtained was dissolved in a 60 per cent. solution of acetic acid and treated with the requisite quantity of freshly prepared manganese dioxide and the whole mass left on water-bath for about 45 minutes. A deep violet coloured solution was obtained which was filtered and saturated with sodium acetate and left overnight. The precipitate dye was collected and dissolved in acetic acid and reprecipitated by a solution of sodium carbonate. The colour base thus obtained was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ligroin. It is dark bluish crystals, dissolves in water and in dilute acetic acid with a deep violet colour. In dilute mineral acid it shows a green colour. It also dissolves in alcohol and chloroform with a violet colour. It melts at

196°-198°. (Found: N, 10·3. $C_{26}H_{27}N_3O$ requires N, 10·5 per cent.).

Condensation of Quinoline-2-aldehyde with Diethylaniline, Methylbenzylaniline and Ethylbenzylaniline.—In a similar way the above mentioned bases were condensed with quinoline-2-aldehyde. The colour bases obtained all dissolved in alcohol or chloroform with deep blue, greenish blue and green colour respectively and melted at 144°-145°, 172°-174° and 252°-254° respectively. [Found: N, 8·9 (Calc. N, 9·3 for $C_{30}H_3N_3O$). Found: N, 7·8 (Calc. N, 8·06 for $C_{36}H_3N_3O$). Found: N, 7·2 (Calc. N, 7·2 for $C_{38}H_{35}N_3O$)]. The colour bases combine with acetic acid and oxalic acid but the compounds thus obtained are not sufficiently stable and decompose easily into the colour base and the acid. The colour bases however dissolve in glacial acetic acid with violet, green-blue and blue colour respectively.

Condensation of Dimethylaniline and w-Tribromoquinaldine.—Quinaldine tribromide (5 g.) and dimethylaniline (5 g.) were heated together on water-bath for about two hours. The excess of dimethylaniline was removed by steam distillation and the residue dissolved in acetic acid and the dye and carbinol base obtained as mentioned above. The carbinol base obtained gave on analysis N=9·95 (calc. N, 10·5 per cent. for $C_{26}H_{27}N_3O$).

In this case the yield is better.

This method was also utilised to get the corresponding dyes from diethylaniline, methylbenzylaniline and ethylbenzylaniline. In the case of diethylaniline the heating was done for about half an hour only. Longer heating decomposes the carbinol base formed, the hydrobromic acid formed reducing it to the leucobase state.

It was therefore necessary to oxidise with a slight amount of freshly prepared manganese dioxide in all the cases mentioned above and thus get the substances as carbinol base completely.

